

Selective Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III) as Thiocyanato and Azido Mixed-Complexes with Hydroxy-amidine

ABHA RANI JHA and RAJENDRA KUMAR MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010, M.P.

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A simple, rapid and selective method for solvent extraction and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of microamounts of iron(III) as thiocyanato and azido mixed-complexes with a newly synthesized extractant, N-hydroxy-N-m-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-dimethyl)phenylbenzamidinium hydrochloride (HOAm) is described. The ratio of chelating extractant and azide or thiocyanate to metal in mixed complex is found to be 1 : 1 : 2 (Fe : HOAm : N_3^-/SCN^-) in benzene. The molar absorbances of azido and thiocyanato mixed-complexes are 4,000 and 12,000 $l.mole^{-1}cm^{-1}$ at 520 and 460 nm respectively. The thiocyanato mixed complex can be extracted quantitatively from 0.1 to 0.4 M HCl. The tolerance of the method to other ions is given.

A number of reagents¹⁻⁶ have been described for the colorimetric determination of iron. The most widely used reagent for iron(III) is thiocyanate. Although the method is simple, it suffers from various limitations such as variation of colour intensity with respect to the concentration of thiocyanate and hydrochloric acid. Several modifications have been suggested to improve the method. Recently, mixed-ligand complex of iron(III) with N-hydroxyethylenediamine-N,N',N'-triacetate and thiocyanate has been reported by Yamamoto and Ohashi⁶. The method is fairly selective, but is less sensitive than the parent thiocyanate method.

N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines have been found to be potential analytical reagents for the determination of various transition elements⁷⁻¹². In this communication, we report a simple, rapid and selective method for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of micro amounts of iron(III) with the newly synthesized reagent, N-hydroxy-N-m-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-dimethyl)phenylbenzamidinium hydrochloride (HOAm), in the presence of thiocyanate and azide. This method has a wider working range of reagent concentration and Beer's law and shorter standing time. The method has been applied for the determination of iron in drugs.

Experimental

Apparatus: An ECIL UV-VIS spectrophotometer model GS-865, with matched 1 cm silica cells, were used for absorbance measurements. A systronic pH meter type-322 was used for pH measurements.

Reagent and chemicals: All the chemicals used were of B. D. H., AnalaR grade. The stock solution of iron was prepared by dissolving iron wire (E. Merck) in 30% nitric acid. The oxides of nitrogen were removed by boiling and the solution was standardised gravimetrically¹³. A 0.1% w/v solution of the reagent^{7,14} was used for extraction purposes.

Procedure: A measured amount of iron(III) was introduced into a 100 ml separatory funnel and was mixed with 2 ml potassium thiocyanate or sodium azide solution (2% w/v), the acidity was adjusted to the required value and the solution diluted with water to 25 ml. The aqueous phase was equilibrated with 25 ml benzene solution of the reagent for 2 min and the organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g) for a few min in a 50 ml beaker. The absorbance was measured at respective λ_{max} against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The reagent showed negligible absorption in the region 450-700 nm. The red-orange thiocyanato and red-purple azido mixed-complexes showed λ_{max} at 460 and 520 nm, respectively. Their relevant spectral data are shown in Table 1.

Effect of variables: Of the various solvents (benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, esters, ethers and alcohols) used, benzene was preferred because the distribution coefficient of metal as complex was high. The acidity of the aqueous phase was maintained with 2 M hydrochloric acid and dilute ammonia. Acetic, nitric and sulphuric acids could not be used due to low absorbance of

* For correspondence.

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA FOR THIOCYANATO AND AZIDO MIXED-COMPLEXES OF IRON(III) WITH HOAM IN BENZENE

Characteristics	Thiocyanate system	Azide system
Optimum acidity (M HCl)/pH	0.1-0.4	4.0-4.8
Colour	Red-orange	Red-purple
λ_{max} , nm	460	520
ϵ , l. mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	12,000	4,000
Sandell's sensitivity μ g of Fe ³⁺ per cm ²	0.0046	0.0139
Optimum concentration range on the basis of Beer's law, ppm	0.2-4.0	0.8-13.0
Relative standard deviation*	$\pm 0.7\%$	$\pm 0.8\%$

* 10 measurements, each containing 2 ppm Fe³⁺ in thiocyanate or 6 ppm Fe³⁺ in azide system.

the complex. The optimum acidity ranges are shown in Table 1.

A 50 and 200 fold molar excess of hydroxy-amidine and thiocyanate or azide respectively were adequate for complete extraction of iron(III). Addition of more reagents caused no adverse effect on the absorbance of the coloured system. The order in which the reagents are mixed was not critical. An equilibrium period of 2 min was sufficient for complete extraction of metal as complex. The extracts were stable for at least 30 hr at 27°. The variation in temperature from 20 to 40° and volume of the aqueous phase from 15 to 60 ml did not affect the optical properties of the mixed-complex. No effect of electrolytes (1-3 M) on the rate of extraction and absorbance of ternary complex was observed. The ternary complex in the organic phase may be formulated as Fe.OAm.(X)₃, where X = SCN⁻ or N₃⁻, on the basis of the stoichiometry obtained by the curve fitting method^{1,5}.

The overall reaction can be expressed as follows:

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions in the determination of iron(III) was studied as described in the recommended procedure. The ions chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulphate, borate, urea, thiourea, lanthanoid, alkali and alkaline earth elements, did not interfere in the determination of iron as thiocyanato or azido mixed-complex. The tolerance limits in ppm of other ions in the thiocyanate system, [0.3 M HCl, 1.7 ppm Fe(III)] and the azide system, [pH=4.5, 3.5 ppm Fe(III)] are shown in parenthesis, in that order: fluoride (400, -); phosphate or arsenate (1200, -); Cu²⁺ (40, -); Zn²⁺ or Cd²⁺ (1000, 800); Fe²⁺ (1000, 800); Ni²⁺ (400, 200); Co²⁺ (400, 200); Mn²⁺ (500, 600); Al³⁺ (400, 400); Cr³⁺ (400, 300); Th⁴⁺ (200, 200); Ti⁴⁺ (100, 150); Zr⁴⁺ (400, 350); Nb⁵⁺ (40, 60); Ta⁵⁺ (100, 150); V⁵⁺ (20, 20); Mo⁶⁺ (20, 40); W⁶⁺ (40, 20); U⁶⁺ (300, 300).

Application of the method to the analysis of drugs: The suggested thiocyanate method was successfully applied to the analysis of tablets or capsules containing ferrous sulphate, ferrous fumarate or ferrous gluconate.

A tablet or a capsule was taken in a Kjeldahl flask and heated gently with conc. HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ (10 : 1 v/v) till charring began. Dropwise addition of HNO₃ acid and boiling was continued till colourless liquid was obtained. A few ml of water was added and the solution was evaporated to white fumes. It was then dissolved in a few ml of dilute hydrochloric acid and diluted to one litre. A 0.5 to 5 ml aliquot of the above solution containing $\approx 50 \mu\text{g}$ iron was taken and iron(III) was determined by the procedure recommended earlier. The accuracy of results were compared with those obtained by using 1 : 10-phenanthroline method as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—APPLICATION OF THE METHOD TO THE DETERMINATION OF IRON IN DRUGS WITH THIOCYANATE METHOD

Sl. No.	Drug	Iron	Calculated* from absorbances with 1 : 10-phenanthroline	Calculated* from absorbances with hydroxyamidine method
1.	Folitrin, Biochem Pharmaceuticals	Ferrous fumarate 0.35 g	0.349 g	0.349 g
2.	Foliplex, Koptan Chemicals Co.	Ferrous fumarate 0.050 g	0.050 g	0.049 g
3.	Calglufer, Sandoz	Ferrous gluconate 0.075 g	0.071 g	0.070 g
4.	Redicyte, Merck Sharp & Dohme	Ferrous sulphate 0.8 g	0.28 g	0.28 g

* = An average of 6 determinations.

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